
**FORMATION OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF ENGLISH
LANGUAGE LEARNERS WITH THE HELP OF TECHNOLOGY FOR THE
DEVELOPMENT OF CRITICAL THINKING**

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Abstract.

The article proposes a technology for the development of critical thinking in teaching English. The problem of developing critical thinking in English lessons in the formation of communicative competence is also considered.

Keywords.

communication environment, competence, critical thinking, English.

Introduction.

According to the new state educational standards, a foreign language is one of the most important subjects in a multilingual world. In the modern educational sphere, a foreign language is perceived as a means of communication, mutual understanding and interaction between representatives of different cultures. A foreign language, like other philological disciplines, forms the student's communicative culture, contributes to his general speech development, broadening his horizons and education, therefore, the leading goal of teaching a foreign language at the present stage of education is the formation of the student's communicative competence in the main types of speech activity [25,3518].

Literature review:

The significance of this goal is explained by the fact that a person should have the opportunity to be a full-fledged subject of communication in the dialogue of cultures. The concept of communicative competence in Russian linguodidactics was first introduced into scientific use by Vyatyutnev M.N. He presents communicative competence "as the choice and implementation of speech behavior programs depending on a person's ability to navigate in a particular communication environment; the ability to classify situations depending on the topic, tasks, communicative attitudes that arise in students before the conversation,

as well as during the conversation in the process of mutual adaptation" [36,45]. In the modern sense, communicative competence is the ability to realize linguistic competence in various conditions of speech communication, taking into account social norms of behavior and the communicative expediency of the statement. E.V. Rudensky believes that communicative competence consists of the ability to: - give a socio-psychological forecast of the communicative situation in which to communicate; - socio-psychologically program the process of communication, based on the originality of the communicative situation; - to carry out socio-psychological management of communication processes in a communicative situation [29,224].

Discussions:

Communicative competence in teaching English is a set of knowledge about the language system and its units, their construction and functioning in speech, about the ways of forming thoughts in the target language and understanding the judgments of others, about the socio-cultural characteristics of native speakers of the target language, about the specifics of various types of discourses. In 1975, Jan Van Eck gave a description of communicative competence based on the specifics of the Council of Europe. He singled out the following competencies: linguistic, sociolinguistic, sociocultural, strategic, discursive, social. Sololova E.N. considers all these competencies "necessary for the formation of a foreign language communicative competence, because each of them is a significant link in the process of learning a foreign language" [33,239].

The difficulty of learning a foreign language at school lies precisely in the fact that it is necessary to create conditions for the formation of communicative competence, i.e. internal readiness and ability to verbal communication. Thus, the question arises about the use of pedagogical technologies that contribute to the formation of communicative competence. One of these technologies is the technology for the development of critical thinking.

The technology for the development of critical thinking was created by American educators at the end of the 20th century. Its founders are Charles Temple, Jeannie Steele, and Curtis Meredith. This technology combines the ideas and methods of technologies of collective and group ways of learning, as well as learning in cooperation and developing learning. The technology for the development of critical thinking is recognized to be considered general pedagogical and above the subject. In Russia, it received its distribution in 1997. Currently, this technology is gaining popularity due to the fact that it is focused on the individual

and helps to solve educational problems: teaching, developing, educational. As noted by G.V. Sorina "critical thinking presupposes the presence of reflection skills regarding one's own mental activity, the ability to work with concepts, judgments, conclusions, questions, and the development of abilities for analytical activity. Critical thinking as a whole is characterized by a practical orientation [34,697].

The main idea of the Technology for the Development of Critical Thinking is to create such an educational process in which students, together with the teacher actively work with great interest on an equal footing, consciously reflect, correlate what they have learned with their own experience ; working with various types of information, confirm, refute or expand knowledge, new ideas, feelings or opinions about the world around; suggest and justify possible solutions to the problem. In this technology, a large role is given to the speech orientation and the interaction of students, which allows the formation of communicative competence.

English language lessons contribute to the development of critical thinking through a variety of materials and interactive approaches.

The technology for the development of critical thinking stands out among innovative pedagogical technologies with a successful combination of problem-based productive learning with lesson technology, effective methods and techniques.

A teacher working within the framework of the Technology for the Development of Critical Thinking should be well aware that his/her work will be productive if s/he chooses correctly: informative material that promotes the development of critical thinking;

- method (separate technique, strategy) of the lesson;
- developed the correct lesson plan.

Working in the critical thinking technology mode, the teacher only activates the activity of students, ceasing to be the main source of information.

Students independently plan their learning activities and are capable of adequate self-assessment.

The teacher only directs the student's actions, using technology techniques that turn learning into a collaborative and interesting search. I.O. Zagashv believes that "the value of this technology is that it teaches to listen and hear, develops speech, enables communication, activates mental activity, cognitive interest, and encourages learners to work. Fear disappears, the student's responsibility for his/her answer increases, the teacher and students participate together in obtaining knowledge" [37, 284].

Conclusion.

All this has a positive effect on the formation of foreign language communicative competence. Thus, using the Technology for the Development of Critical Thinking in English language lessons, the teacher develops the personality of the student, first, when teaching a foreign language, resulting in the formation of communicative competence, which provides favorable conditions for cognitive activity and self-improvement. The teacher stimulates the interests of the student, develops his/her desire to practically use the target language, as well as to study, thereby making it possible to achieve success in mastering the subject.

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